

**E-GOVERNANCE INITIATIVES OF HUBLI DHARWAD
MUNICIPAL CORPORATION: AN ANALYSIS**
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ABSTRACT:

As a dynamic field of study, Public Administration is rooted in the principles of “perform, reform, and transform,” embodying values such as transparency, citizen participation, and accountability through Information and Communication Technology (ICT). Terms like administration, government, and governance are prominent in the public administration lexicon. The introduction of the National e-Governance Plan in 2006, followed by various digital initiatives and contemporary AI-based governance models, has redefined public service delivery. Today, e-governance is widely recognized as the crux of good governance. This research paper examines the e-governance initiatives undertaken by the Hubli Dharwad Municipal Corporation (HDMC), specifically focusing on E-Janam, E-Nirmaan, E-Vyapar, and E-Aasthi.

KEYWORDS:

E-Janam, E-Nirmaan, E-Vyapar, E-Aasthi, Digital Age, AI,
E-Governance.

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1. Introduction

The essence of good governance lies in the paradigm of “minimum government, maximum governance.” Good governance focuses not only on state development but also on improving the quality of public life. To realize the goals of good governance, e-governance has emerged as a crucial tool. This research paper explores the various digital initiatives adopted by the Hubli Dharwad Municipal Corporation to provide public services in a more efficient and effective manner.

2. Literature Review & Research Methodology

A comprehensive literature review plays a vital role in understanding theoretical concepts and structuring research within an academic framework. For this study, both primary and secondary sources were

widely consulted. Key references include All About E-Governance (Rahul Rajan, 2023), Role of E-Governance & Digital India in Empowering Indian Citizens (Vanyavarma, 2021), E-Governance Plans in Karnataka (Yogaraju, 2015), and the National E-Governance Plan in India (Radha, 2009). Additionally, various books, websites, research articles, non-state stakeholder reports, and state government documents related to e-governance were reviewed.

3. Objectives

1. To understand the effective implementation of e-governance initiatives at the Hubli Dharwad Municipal Corporation.
2. To assess the impact of these e-governance initiatives on the corporation's Human Resource and Capital Resource Management.
3. To analyze existing challenges and suggest prospects for future improvement.

4. E-Governance Initiatives in Hubli Dharwad Municipal Corporation

This section focuses on the core e-governance initiatives undertaken by the Hubli Dharwad Municipal Corporation in its routine administration. The e-office framework within the corporation operates at three levels: sectional, zonal, and commissionerate. The key initiatives analyzed include:

E-Janam Yojana: Announced in the corporation's 2023-2024 annual financial statement, this portal enables parents to apply for birth and death certificates within 21 days. All hospitals within city limits are linked to this software, allowing them to transfer data directly to the corporation. The section office then conducts a detailed examination before issuing the certificate. However, the corporation can only amend these certificates based on judicial orders. For death certificates, a clear procedure is followed whether the death occurs at a hospital or at home. Hospitals transfer the data electronically, while for home deaths, concerned officials visit the family for scrutiny before issuing the certificate.

E-Nirmaan Yojana: To streamline building construction management, the corporation introduced the E-Nirmaan software. Applicants upload relevant documents to the portal, and concerned officials scrutinize the applications and inspect the construction sites. Subsequently, the zonal commissioner issues the required building

certificates.

E-Vyapar Yojana: Through this initiative, the corporation invites applications from the public for establishing trade, commerce, and other businesses. By cross-examining the relevant documents within legal frameworks and clauses, entrepreneurs and developers are granted the necessary trade permits.

E-Aasthi Yojana: This is a flagship program for both the Hubli Dharwad Municipal Corporation and the Government of Karnataka. Since a primary purpose of local governments is to generate local resources and sustain the governance ecosystem, the E-Aasthi program is vital. The corporation collects a major share of its property taxes through this initiative. Using unique Property Identification (PID) numbers, citizens can seamlessly pay their annual property and related taxes online.

5. Suggestions & Prospects

Based on the study of e-governance implementation at the Hubli Dharwad Municipal Corporation, the following suggestions are proposed for better prospects:

1. **Administrative & Financial Empowerment:** The e-governance cell requires stronger administrative and financial backing for optimal functioning.
2. **Resource Management:** More efficient management of human resources is needed to handle digital workflows.
3. **Time-Bound Delivery:** Ensuring strict, time-bound service delivery for all e-initiatives is the need of the hour.
4. **Budget Allocation:** A minimum of 10% of the municipal budget should be allocated specifically to the e-governance cell.
5. **Simplified Procedures:** Simplifying bureaucratic procedures will promote more economic, efficient, and effective governance.

6. Conclusion

The concept of a welfare state accelerates the government's push toward better, more experiential, and responsible administration. E-governance serves as a vital instrument for achieving good governance. Furthermore, the impacts of globalization, liberalization, and privatization have compelled administrations worldwide to transition toward digital governance models. Despite some functional limitations and minor

demerits observed in this study, the Hubli Dharwad Municipal Corporation is successfully operating its e-initiatives on a highly commendable scale.

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The Authors have no conflict of interest to declare that they are relevant to the content of this article.

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